

**MODERN INTERPRETATION OF TEACHING
ADJECTIVES IN THE KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE****Saparmatov Omar Shamurat ugli****Student of the Karakalpak Language and Literature Department of the
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ABSTRACT

In this article, modern approaches to teaching adjectives in the Karakalpak language are analyzed. The text highlights the effectiveness of using personality-oriented and competency-based approaches, interactive methods, role-playing games, problem-based learning, and information and communication technologies. The article also shows ways to strengthen students' morphological knowledge, develop speech culture, and form aesthetic taste through these approaches.

In the Karakalpak language, an adjective is a set of words expressing the qualities and characteristics of an object, phenomenon, or person, and plays an important role in the morphological and lexical system of the language. Teaching adjectives serves not only to increase grammatical knowledge, but also to develop students' speech culture, enrich means of expression, and form aesthetic taste. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce modern approaches to teaching the topics of adjectives.

Based on the modern interpretation, personality-oriented and competency-based approaches are used in teaching adjectives. The personality-oriented approach takes into account the individual characteristics, interests, and needs of the student, encouraging their active participation in the lesson. The competency-based approach helps students develop skills in the practical application of adjectives, text composition, and analysis.

Interactive methods are effective in teaching qualitative topics. For example, the visual branching and grouping of adjectives using the "cluster" method makes it easier for students to study the morphological category. The methods of "brainstorming" and "discussion" teach students to apply various qualities in accordance with the situation, encouraging them to think actively.

Role-playing games and dramatization methods are also used in teaching adjectives. For example, students use adjectives correctly by preparing short dialogues or scenes on the topic "Market", "Family", or "School". In this way, students not only strengthen grammatical knowledge, but also develop speech culture.

With the help of information and communication technologies, it is possible to conduct lessons more vividly and interestingly. Multimedia presentations, animations, and interactive

tests allow students to visually explain the meaning of adjectives and their use within sentences.

The problem-based learning approach is effectively used in teaching the topic of quality. The teacher gives students various problem situations and encourages them to independently find the correct use of adjectives. For example, questions like “Which adjective complements this sentence better?” or “Which adjective makes sense when used with this verb?” develop students' analytical thinking.

In conclusion, the modern interpretation of teaching adjectives in the Karakalpak language includes a personality-oriented approach, a competency-based approach, interactive methods, role-playing games, and information and communication technologies. These approaches serve to strengthen students' morphological knowledge, improve their speech culture, and develop their aesthetic taste..

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